

SECURING THE INTERNET OF THINGS: A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW OF SECURITY CHALLENGES AND SOLUTIONS

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Abstract

Various industries have been transformed by the speedy growth of IOT (Internet of things) and has enabled connectivity, industry automation, and analytical decision-making. However, many security threats including, Access denied, Security breaches of data, DDoS (Distributed Denial of Service) threats and ransomware have been introduced by the production of IoT devices. In this paper, we will review the IoT security threats and discuss about the emerging attacks. Also, we will look into the solutions like blockchain, ML (Machine Learning), edge computing and some lightweight encryption techniques. Lastly, we will compare the various threats and their solutions to present you a complete picture of IoT security landscape and also highlights unresolved issues and proposed future work in the domain.

INTRODUCTION

Use of IoT (Internet of Things) has rapidly reshaped the whole industry by connecting them with IoT devices all around, developing an ecosystem of industry automation and enhancing the decision-making for the businesses. Many sectors of businesses are using IoT devices now including health-care system, industry, transportation system, smart homes, and cities. According to an estimate, growingly over 75 billion IoT devices will be functioning all over the world by 2025. IoT devices are playing vital role in modern organizations[1].

We can increase functional efficiency, data collection (real-time) and tasks of industry automation, reducing human intervention and quick response with the use of IoT devices. Multiple examples can be taken like in healthcare, patients are monitored, smart patient beds and some wearable to monitoring the patient

remotely from far away has improved the convenience and quality of patient care[2][3]. Also, management of resources, including optimization of traffic, distributing energy and monitoring of public safety in smart cities has been improved with IoT devices [4].

No doubt, the IoT devices has offered great opportunities, the considerable number of interconnected devices facing important security and privacy challenges. Devices with limited functional resources are often lack strong security mechanisms like up-to-date encryption or authentication protocols [2]. This increases the chances of cyber-attacks, important data can be stolen, access to an unauthorized person, DDoS attacks and some other unexpected malicious activities [5].

Due to no standardization in IoT devices, these threats have high probability to occur. Some device manufacturer companies produce the IoT devices with basic security solutions, that discrepancies lead to devices exposed to threats like botnet attacks as an example of Mirai botnet attack [5]. Due to the vulnerabilities of these IoT device and chances of DDoS attacks at large scale, enhanced security measures are highlighted [6].

Many times, the devices are installed in very limited re- sources environments, where it is not possible to execute strong encryption algorithms or strong security protocols due to power and processing constraints. It can be observed mostly in applications of smart sensors or individual control systems, where cheap and low in power devices are mostly used [7]. Due to this, many devices cannot defend the cyber-attacks like ransomware, MitM (Man-in-the-middle) attacks, or side- channel attacks [4].

There are many security solutions are proposed by re- search scholars to address these issues including blockchain technology, machine learning based IDS (Intrusion Detection System) and light-weight encryption techniques personalized for environments with limited resources[8] [5]. Although these proposed solutions are promising however challenges are there, like mostly of scalability, power efficient and capability to handle evolving threats.

In this paper, we have reviewed the security challenges of IoT devices and discussed the proposed solutions in the literature. We will also discuss the evolving threats and attacks and highlight the progress in security of the devices.

The research questions that are considered in this review paper including what are the major security threats and vulner- abilities across the three layers of IoT architecture (Perception, Network, and Application)? what are the trade-offs of using lightweight encryption techniques in resource- constrained IoT devices? what advancements are required in quantum-resistant encryption algorithms to secure IoT devices against future quantum computing threats?

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. IoT Architecture and Security Vulnerabilities
There are following three layers in the architecture of IoT: 1: - Perception Layer

2: - Network Layer

3: - Application Layer

Vulnerabilities of all these three layers are unique and different that makes IoT devices vulnerable to the cyber- attacks.

1) **Perception Layer:** Consists of physical sensors and devices that gather the actual data from any work space. These IoT devices are mostly situated in unsecured places, so the chances of physical tampering, Jamming and side-channel attacks [7]. Moreover, many devices having processing power constraints, due to which it is difficult to implement strong crypto-graphic defenses.

2) **Network Layer:** Data transmitted from devices to servers in this layer. MitM (Man in the middle), DDoS (Dis- tributed Denial of Service) and routing attack vulnerabilities found in this layer [5] [4]. A security breach in this network layer can compromise the data integrity and data availability due to entire IoT ecosystem may be disrupt.

3) **Application Layer:** Data gathered from devices is pro- cessed in this layer and services are provided to end user. Malware, access to unauthorized and data security breaches vulnerabilities found at this layer [2]. Healthcare systems or Financial Systems are mostly found vulnerable to Violating privacy and regulatory breaches [2].

B. Key IoT Security Threats and Attacks

IoT devices have a huge threat of cyber-attacks, who are able to exploit these vulnerabilities all over the different layers. Key attacks with proposed solution in the literature is compared in Table 1.

C. Emerging Threats and New Attack Vectors

1) **Advanced Persistent Threats:** APTs are highly devel- oped attacks where an intruder gains unauthorized access to a system and remains undetected for an extended period. These attacks are difficult to detect and reduce, as they operate under the radar for long periods, slowly collect important data or damage the key systems [3].

2) **Botnet Attacks:** IoT botnets are collections of infected devices controlled by an attacker. Once the devices are hacked these are used to launch organized attacks, like DDoS attacks or stealing data. The Mirai

Botnet was one of the most prominent examples, exploit default passwords and unsecured firmware to take control numbers of IoT devices [5].

3) **Eavesdropping and Sniffing:** Attackers can intercept unsecured communication between IoT devices, access to private information. Many IoT devices transfer data over insecure channels, making these devices vulnerable to eavesdropping and sniffing attacks.

D. IoT Security Solutions

1) **Blockchain Technology:** Blockchain is slowly being embraced to secure IoT networks due to its decentralized nature. Blockchain allows for secure and resistant data exchange between devices, ensuring that no single entity should be manipulated or change the data [8]. It is important and helpful in situations where trust between IoT devices is important, like in supply chain tracking and healthcare monitoring systems [3]. Blockchain has been successfully applied in managing IoT devices in complex supply chains, where secure tracking of goods and equipment is difficult. It ensures that each step in the supply chain is recorded in an Unchangeable record to avoid fraud and tampering [4].

2) **Machine Learning (ML):** Potential threats and anomalies in IoT devices networks can be detected through Machine learning which is a very powerful tool. Algorithms of ML can be trained to detect the unusual traffic flow leading to DDoS attacks or attempt to access of some unauthorized person [5]. Moreover, models of ML improve themselves continuously through learning from past data that makes them capable to deal with new and evolving attack techniques. The data is processed locally through edge computing, real time threats detection can be achieved through ML models and also reduce the responsiveness to new coming attacks [7]. This is so valuable especially where IoT devices working in autonomous environment like smart grids or industrial control systems.

3) **Edge Computing:** Latency in edge computing is reduced when data processing brought closer to IoT devices, that limits the sending of sensitive data to cloud servers. This enhances the device performance as well as security is improved through reducing the

risk of data interception during communication [7]. For real-time processing applications, edge computing is found very useful like autonomous vehicles or smart city infrastructures. It is ensured in edge computing that all data should be processed locally so that it could remain in the same network and can be protected from unauthorized access [6].

4) **Lightweight Encryption Techniques:** A large number of IoT devices has weak computational power that is needed for encryption methods. Therefore, some light-weight encryption methods are being designed to meet the requirement of acceptable security while burden on the resources of IoT devices is minimized [4]. Advanced Encryption Standard (AES) and elliptic curve cryptography are included in these techniques to provide security for IoT communication and not compromising the device performance. [9] has analysed the existing lightweight encryption algorithms including AES, PRESENT, LBlock, SIMON, XTEA, PRINCE, Piccolo, HIGHT, RECT-

ANGLE and Skipjack to identify their trade-offs for IoT devices. PRESENT, XTEA, and RECTANGLE require low memory and consume low energy hence capable to operate on resource constraint IoT devices. AES can consume high energy but offers robust security. Moreover, [10] introduced a novel algorithm (SIT) for resource-constrained IoT devices. SIT is more powerful to operate on real-time IoT devices ensuring strong security with minimal resources utilization. Performance of these light-weight algorithms can be compared and analysed in the Table II.

III. METHODOLOGY

In this review paper, our main focus was to investigate the security and privacy challenges inherent in the Internet of Things (IoT). The review aims to identify security issues across IoT layers, also assess existing security frameworks, and propose improved solutions for IoT systems.

The data was collected from various journals like IEEE, MDPI, Frontiers, Springer and arxiv for a critical understanding of the breadth and depth of IoT security issues. Using this data ensures a broad view of current challenges and potential security issues

and solutions, making it highly relevant to the study's objectives.

The primary data for this review paper was obtained from papers published in from 2016 to 2024. For Tools such as bibliographic databases (e.g., IEEE

Xplore and Google Scholar) and citation tracking and formatting (like Latex) software were employed to collect and organize the literature.

TABLE I
COMPARISON OF MAJOR IOT ATTACKS AND SOLUTIONS

Attack Type	Description	Notable Examples	Proposed Solutions
Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS)	Attackers overwhelm a target with excessive traffic, causing services to become unavailable.	Mirai Botnet (2016)	Blockchain for secure data flow [8], AI-based traffic detection [5].
Data Breaches	Unauthorized access to sensitive data due to weak encryption or insecure communication protocols.	IoT healthcare data breaches	Advanced encryption like Diffie-Hellman [4]), edge computing [7].
Ransomware	Attackers gain control of IoT devices and demand a ransom to restore functionality.	Increasing attacks on IoT devices	Blockchain for decentralized control [8], improved authentication [2].
Side-Channel Attacks	Exploits information leakage through power consumption, electromagnetic emissions, or timing data.	Low-resource IoT devices	Lightweight cryptography [6], ML-based anomaly detection [5].
Man-in-the-Middle (MitM)	Attackers intercept communication between two devices, allowing unauthorized access to sensitive data or manipulation of communications.	MitM attacks in industrial IoT	Secure communication protocols [4], TLS/SSL encryption [2].
Routing Attacks	Attackers compromise the routing process, redirecting data to malicious nodes, disrupting communication.	Wormhole attacks in IoT networks	Securing routing protocols [7], blockchain for trust management [8].
Physical Attacks	Attackers physically tamper with or destroy IoT devices, resulting in data corruption, leakage, or denial of service.	Physical tampering with sensors	Device tamper-proofing [6], encryption at the perception layer [7].

TABLE II
PERFORMANCE METRICS OF LIGHT-WEIGHT ENCRYPTION ALGORITHMS

Algorithm	Energy Consumption	Memory Utilization	Execution Time	Throughput	Security Level
AES	High	High	Moderate	High	Strong
PRESENT	Low	Low	Moderate	Moderate	Adequate
XTEA	Very Low	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate	Adequate
RECTANGLE	Low	Low	Moderate	Moderate	Adequate

Skipjack	Very Low	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate	Adequate
SPECK	Low	Moderate	Moderate	High	Adequate
SIMON	Low	Moderate	Moderate	High	Adequate
TEA	Moderate	Moderate	High	Moderate	Adequate
RSA	Very High	Very High	Very High	Low	Very Strong
ECC	High	High	Moderate	Low	Very Strong
SIT	Very Low	Very Low	Fast	Moderate	Strong

A. Process and Criteria

A literature review was performed to ensure the involvement of high-quality and relevant sources. The selection criteria for the review paper were including review papers that are published between 2016 and 2024 to include recent advancements. Addressed security and privacy challenges across distinct IoT layers (e.g., perception, network, application). Focused on emerging solutions such as lightweight Encryption algorithms, blockchain, edge computing, and machine learning. Highlighted vulnerabilities and mitigation strategies for IoT devices and systems. The study reviewed over 20 articles, narrowing down to approximately 10 primary sources that directly addressed the research objectives. The article evaluates recommended security solutions by examining their effectiveness against IoT threats. One solution under consideration is

blockchain technology, which can safeguard decentralized IoT networks. Uses Machine Learning (ML) to detect anomalies and mitigate threats in real time. Edge Computing improves latency and data security. Lightweight encryption algorithms designed for IoT devices with limited resources. Energy consumption, scalability, and adaptability were among the performance parameters assessed during the review. Where available, existing data collection from reviewed articles were used. For instance, analysis data collection and case studies related to IoT attacks were integrated. The datasets were chosen based on their relevance, integrity, and completeness. This secondary data approach ensures coverage of broader scenarios without the need for new empirical data collection.

Fig. 1. PERFORMANCE METRICS OF LIGHT-WEIGHT ENCRYPTION ALGORITHMS

The collected literature was classified based on the IoT architecture’s layers (perception, network, application, and others). Specific attention was given to identifying security issues unique to each layer and the countermeasures proposed. Steps were taken to ensure ethical handling of all secondary data. For sensitive data, such as privacy-related

case studies, information was anonymized, and its use was aligned with open-access permissions granted by the original sources. This mixed-methods approach was chosen to combine the strengths of qualitative and quantitative data. The comprehensive review of literature ensures the inclusion of diverse

perspectives and the identification of commonalities and gaps in IoT security research. By focusing on secondary data, the study leverages existing knowledge to draw meaningful insights without duplicating prior efforts.

The chosen methodology addresses the research question effectively by providing a multi-layered understanding of IoT vulnerabilities, highlighting the state-of-the-art solutions and their limitations and identifying open challenges and future research directions.

I. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

IoT devices are facing a variety of security threats including side-channel attacks to ransomware and DDoS attacks. Although we have many proposed solutions to handle these threats like Blockchain, Machine Learning models and lightweight encryption but there are still some gaps remain. No standardized security protocols and development of quantum computing are few of the reasons that are pose significant threats to the security of IoT Devices. Developing the quantum-resistant encryption algorithms including improvement of trust management in decentralized networks for IoT devices and development of energy efficient security protocols for resource-constrained devices may be focused in future research.

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